

Effective assay for olive vinegar production from olive oil mill wastewaters

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Abstract

In this work, an effective and simple approach for vinegar production from olive oil press-mill wastewaters (OMW) is presented. Effects of sterilization and yeast presence on the acetic acid production were investigated. Sugar addition and inoculum of selected yeast starter have been crucial for a satisfactory acidification. In the obtained olive vinegar, the pH and total acidity were 2.92 and 5.6%, respectively. A considerable high level of ash (2%) and total phenols (3,600 mg/L as GAE) characterized olive vinegar, in comparison with samples of apple, wine and balsamic commercial vinegars. Moreover, a high presence of hydroxytyrosol (1,019 mg/L) was obtained. This abundant presence of antioxidants makes olive vinegar a promising nutraceutical and environmentally-friendly product , based upon a waste material such as OMW.

Keywords: acetic fermentation; hydroxytyrosol; phenols; olive oil mill wastewaters; olive vinegar.

29 **Introduction**

30 Vinegar is a common sour-tasting liquid obtained from the biological oxidation of ethanol via two-
31 step **process**: (i) anaerobic conversion of sugars to ethanol by yeasts (*Saccharomyces* species) and
32 (ii) aerobic oxidation of ethanol to acetic acid by bacteria (*Acetobacter* species). It is well known
33 that several types of bacteria species can produce acetic acid by operating directly on sugar-water
34 solutions (Ho, Lazim, Fazry, Zaki, & Lim, 2017). Generally, depending on the raw materials,
35 vinegars are classified in 'grain vinegar', obtained from sorghum, rice, wheat, or other grains, and
36 'fruit vinegars', obtained from fermented grape or apple juices. Coconut and cane vinegars are also
37 produced. Prestigious thousand-year-old vinegars are the Italian balsamic of Modena; Spanish
38 sherry vinegar of the Jerez region; Japanese Kurosu; Chinese vinegars, known as Sichuan Baoning,
39 Shanxi, Zhenjiang and Fujian Yongchun Monascus (Solieri & Giudici, 2009).

40 From ancient time, numerous vinegars **have been considered as a health drink and used for medical**
41 **purposes** (Budak, Aykin, Seydim, Greene, & Guzel-Seydim, 2014). Indeed, numerous studies have
42 evidenced antibacterial, anti-infection and antioxidant activity; lipid metabolism regulation; weight
43 loss; anticancer and antidiabetic effects; lowering cholesterol levels in blood (Johnston & Gaas,
44 2006; Kondo, Tayama, Tsukamoto, Ikeda, & Yamori, 2001; Östman, Granfeldt, Persson, & Björck,
45 2005; Petsiou, Mitrou, Raptis, & Dimitriadis, 2014; Salbe, Johnston, Buyukbese, Tsitouras, &
46 Harman, 2009). Organic acids, polyphenols, melanoidins, ligustrazine, caffeoylsophorose, and
47 tryptophol are few of the bio-active compounds identified in vinegars (Chen, Chen, Giudici, &
48 Chen, 2016).

49 There is a growing interest in the development of novel vinegars from alternative substrates; just to
50 give some examples, onion juice, rubberwood, tomato, strawberry, pineapple, sweet potato have
51 been investigated (Horiuchi, Kanno, & Kobayashi, 1999; Lee, Cho, Jeong, Lee, Jeong, Shim, et al.,
52 2013; Ratanapisit, Apiraksakul, Rerngnarong, Chungsiriporn, & Bunyakarn, 2009; Roda, Lucini,
53 Torchio, Dordoni, De Faveri, & Lambri, 2017; Ubeda, Callejón, Hidalgo, Torija, Troncoso, &
54 Morales, 2013; Ye, Morimura, Han, Shigematsu, & Kida, 2004). **To date, olive mill** byproducts are

55 not sufficiently investigated for this aim, except the work of Pipko (Pipko, 2007), that patented a
56 method for producing vinegar from olive pomace by adding sugar and water before the
57 fermentation.

58 Olive oil processing generates a large amount of wastes, as wastewater and pomace, raising
59 different environmental problems due to the high value of chemical oxygen demand (COD) and the
60 strong antimicrobial and phytotoxic properties (Cuomo, Venditti, Ceglie, De Leonardis, Macciola,
61 & Lopez, 2015; Cuomo, Venditti, Cinelli, Ceglie, & Lopez, 2016; Filidei, Masciandaro, &
62 Ceccanti, 2003). Olive oil mill wastewaters (OMW) are a sub-acidic (pH 4.80 - 5.50) and red-to-
63 black colored liquid, resulting from both the olive fruit's water and the water added during oil
64 processing. Indicatively, OMW have a high dry residue, ranging from 4.1 to 16.4%, and the phenols
65 are the major components. Hydroxytyrosol, tyrosol, phenolic acids, secoiridoids and flavonoids
66 were identified among the phenolic compounds and several techniques were assayed for their
67 economically viable recovery (Allouche, Fki, & Sayadi, 2004; De Leonardis, Macciola, Lembo,
68 Aretini, & Nag, 2007; De Leonardis, Macciola, & Nag, 2009).

69 Aim of this study was to produce phenol-enriched vinegar from olive oil mill wastewaters at
70 laboratory scale. The obtained vinegar was characterized by analytical and microbiological analysis
71 in comparison with few commercial vinegars.

72 **2. Materials and methods**

73 **2.1. Materials**

74 The olive oil mill wastewaters (OMW), collected in October 2014 from an oil mill sited in the
75 Molise region (South Italy), were stored at 18 °C before use. Selected dry strain of *Saccharomyces*
76 *cerevisiae* and yeast nutrient supplement (Supervit fermentation activator) were from Enartis-
77 Esseco Srl (San Martino Trecate, Novara, Italy). Apple, wine and balsamic vinegars were purchased
78 from a local store. Standard compounds were from Sigma–Aldrich Co (St. Louis, MO, USA).

79 **2.2 Acetification procedure**

80 Frozen OMW were thawed out and decanted leaving the filing on the bottom of the vessel. Two
81 separate procedures were considered for the production of olive vinegar by using alternatively
82 sterilized (OMW-S) or crude (OMW-C) OMW, respectively (see Fig.1). In details, about four liters
83 of OMW were autoclaved at 121 °C for 15 min (OMW-S), while other four liters were used directly
84 (OMW-C). In both the OMW-S and OMW-C, sugar (20 g sucrose per 100 mL OMW) and yeast
85 nutrient supplement (0.05 g per 100 mL OMW) were added. A wine vinegar produced and stored in
86 our laboratory was dissolved in OMW-S (8% v/v), whereas, in order to have the same final volume,
87 similar amount of water (8% v/v) was added in OMW-C. Finally, for each lines of samples (crude
88 and sterilized), one-half was inoculated with the yeast starter (0.01% w/v) (OMW-S-Y and OMW-
89 C-Y, starter fermentation) and, the other half no (OMW-S-noY and OMW-C-noY, spontaneous
90 fermentation). Yeast inoculum was carried out according to the manufacturer's directions by
91 suspending preliminarily dry yeast in 10-times-its-weight warm water (36 °C) for 20 minutes. All
92 OMW samples were left to ferment in open flask under 30 °C temperature by monitoring weekly
93 the acetic acid formation. After four weeks (28 days), only the OMW-C-Y was poured off in 500-
94 mL closed bottles, stored at room temperature in the dark for 15 months, and finally, filtered on
95 paper.

96 ***2.3 Analytical and microbial determinations***

97 All analytical determinations were carried out in duplicate by expressing the result as mean and
98 standard deviation. pH, density, dry residue, total acidity, nitrogen, total protein, ash and ash
99 alkalinity were determined according to wine vinegar official methods (Gazzetta Ufficiale, 1971).
100 Acetic acid (enzymatic method) and volatile compounds (gas-chromatographic method) were
101 determined following the methods described in Iorizzo et al. (Iorizzo, Macciola, Testa, Lombardi, &
102 De Leonardis, 2014). Total phenols and hydroxytyrosol were quantified according De Leonardis et
103 al. (De Leonardis, Macciola, Cuomo, & Lopez, 2015), while the method described in Iorizzo et al.
104 (Iorizzo, Lombardi, Macciola, Testa, Lustrato, Lopez, et al., 2016) was followed for microbial
105 count.

106 **3. Results and discussion**

107 **3.1 Acetification process**

108 For this study, OMW obtained from a traditional olive mill-press has been used. This type of mill is
109 still largely in use in Italy and Portugal, although it is progressively set aside in favor of the
110 continuous two-phase or three-phase system. Physical, chemical and microbiological parameters
111 determined in the thawed and decanted OMW are displayed in Table 1. According to reports from
112 Di Giovacchino et al. (Di Giovacchino, Mascolo, & Seghetti, 1988) the studied OMV showed a
113 sub-acid pH and high dry residue, phenol content and ash. Reducing sugar, ranging generally from
114 15 to 35 g/L (Di Giovacchino et al., 1988), were not determined. Nevertheless, we preferred to add
115 sucrose (20%, w/v) as a support to initial yeast multiplication.

116 In Fig. 1 a schematic representation of the proposed assay is shown. As reported in this illustration,
117 importance of sterilization procedure, spontaneous fermentation (OMW-C-noY and OMW-S-noY),
118 yeast-induced fermentation (OMW-C-Y and OMW-S-Y) and supplied addition (sugar and wine
119 vinegar) is outlined.

120 Trend of acetification was monitored through pH measurements for four weeks (data not shown); at
121 the end of this period, only into the crude inoculated OMW (OMW-C-Y) a significant amount of
122 acetic acid production was obtained (about 2.0%). No acetification in OMW-S-noY and OMW-S-Y
123 was obtained highlighting that the sterilization procedure might undo the presence of yeast starter.
124 However, at this stage, we are unable to demonstrate if the absence of acetification in OMW-S-Y
125 was due to the impact of high temperature treatment in autoclave or to the presence of wine-vinegar
126 supplied as *Acetobacter* source. Moreover, after the heating treatment, a spontaneous solid
127 precipitate, composed probably from macro-compounds as proteins, pigments, gums and impurities,
128 was obtained in the sterilized samples, whereas water supernatant appeared more limpid.
129 Furthermore, neither the natural occurring water microbiota (OMW-C-noY) nor the supplied wine-
130 vinegar used for the sterilized OMW (OMW-S-noY) showed to be able to develop a satisfactory
131 fermentation, confirming the fundamental role of the yeast starter used in this study (Fig. 1).

132 **3.2 Olive vinegar characteristics**

133 The OMW-C-Y sample, hereafter called *olive vinegar*, was characterized after a storage of 15
134 months in dark and cool place (Table 2). Due to the lack of published data on olive vinegar, few
135 common commercial vinegars were analyzed for comparison. At a first glance, one can see that pH
136 and total acidity (as acetic acid) of olive vinegar were 2.92 and 5.6%, respectively. These values
137 were comparable with those of apple and wine vinegars and may be considered satisfactory taking
138 into account that total acidity value for vinegar **must be a** minimum 5.0 % (w/v) (Ho, Lazim, Fazry,
139 Zaki, & Lim, 2017). Dry residue and density values obtained in olive vinegar, due to the effect
140 induced by the supplied sugar source, were higher than those of other vinegars and of starting
141 OMW (Tab.1); these evidences, similarly to other fermented beverages, were indicative of an
142 incomplete fermentation (Iorizzo et al., 2014). Moreover, viable bacterial and yeast cells were not
143 detected into the olive vinegar (data not shown).

144 Since acetoin, diacetyl and ethyl acetate have proved to be useful to characterize the bacterial
145 strains involved in the acetification process (Antonelli, Zeppa, Gerbi, & Carnacini, 1997), these
146 volatile compounds were also detected for olive vinegar (Table 2). Finally, ash content for olive
147 vinegar (2.0%) was found to be about ten-times higher compared with other vinegars. Several
148 studies **have shown that** K is the major mineral of the OMW, followed by P, Na, Ca, Mg, Fe and
149 traces of Cu, Mn and Zn confirming that olive vinegars is a good mineral source (Di Giovacchino et
150 al., 1988; Paredes, Cegarra, Roig, Sánchez-Monedero, & Bernal, 1999).

151 **3.3 Olive vinegar phenol composition**

152 As reported in Table 2, one can easily appreciate the very considerable high level of total phenols
153 (3,600 **mg/L** as GAE) in olive vinegar in comparison with apple, white wine and balsamic vinegars.
154 The HPLC chromatogram for olive vinegar (Fig. 2) displayed a high presence of hydroxytyrosol
155 (1,019 mg/L). Actually, this compound was already abundant in the starting OMW (data not
156 shown). Recently we demonstrated that hydroxytyrosol is highly resistant to the photocatalysis
157 induced by TiO₂ (Cuomo et al., 2016) and that enzymatic oxidation could affected its depletion (De

158 Leonardis et al., 2015). Significant presence of hydroxytyrosol after such a long storage period (15
159 months) evidenced a strong stability of this phenol, also well-known for its antioxidant properties
160 (De Leonardis et al., 2007; De Leonardis et al., 2009). Under a nutritional point of view, high
161 content of hydroxytyrosol in olive vinegar is a winning feature by considering that European Union
162 Commission (European Union Commission, 2012), with regard to the extra virgin olive oil healthy
163 properties, stated recently that '*daily intake of 5 mg of hydroxytyrosol and its derivatives is able to*
164 *prevent low density lipoprotein (LDL) oxidation*'.

165

166 **4. Conclusion**

167 Vinegar from olive oil mill wastewaters has been produced in laboratory-scale. Sugar and nutritive
168 supplement addition and inoculum of selected yeast starter have been crucial for a satisfactory
169 acidification. A considerable benefit of olive vinegar was the huge presence of mineral compounds
170 and phenol substances, especially hydroxytyrosol. Therefore, olive vinegar may be considered a
171 potential nutraceutical and/or novel food/ingredient, agreeable to the Western consumer. Moreover,
172 olive vinegar could represent a possible alternative for the OMW recycling.

173

174 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

175 **Fig.1.** Schematic representation of olive vinegar production.

176 **Fig 2.** Chromatogram (absorbance at 280 nm wavelength) of phenols from olive vinegar directly
177 injected into the HPLC system.

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Table 1. Physical-chemical and microbial characteristics of crude OMW (mean \pm standard deviation).

<u>Physical-chemical parameters</u>	
pH	5.16 \pm 0.52
Total acidity (% acetic acid)	0.2 \pm 0.0
Density (kg/L)	1.036 \pm 0.052
Dry residue (%)	11.2 \pm 0.78
Total lipids (%)	0.3 \pm 0.0
Total nitrogen (g/L)	0.7 \pm 0.0
Total protein (N x 6.25) (g/L)	4.4 \pm 0.4
Ash (%)	3.2 \pm 0.2
Total phenols (mg/L GAE*)	3,830 \pm 306
<u>Microbial count (CFU/mL)</u>	
Yeast	8.1(\pm 0.4) x 10 ⁷
Bacterial	8.0(\pm 0.4) x 10 ⁶

*GAE = gallic acid equivalent

Table 2. Characteristics of the analyzed vinegars (mean \pm standard deviation).

	vinegar			
	<i>olive</i>	<i>apple</i>	<i>white wine</i>	<i>balsamic</i>
pH	2.92 \pm 0.18	3.06 \pm 0.18	2.84 \pm 0.23	3.12 \pm 0.31
Total acidity (% as acetic acid)	5.6 \pm 0.3	5.2 \pm 0.5	7.2 \pm 0.4	7.6 \pm 0.5
Density (kg/L)	1.085 \pm 0.109	1.013 \pm 0.061	1.013 \pm 0.081	1.058 \pm 0.053
Dry residue (%)	20.8 \pm 1.7	1.8 \pm 0.1	0.9 \pm 0.1	10.4 \pm 0.6
Ash (%)	2.0 \pm 0.1	0.3 \pm 0.0	0.2 \pm 0.0	0.6 \pm 0.1
Ash alkalinity (meq/L)	82.4 \pm 6.6	30.2 \pm 3.0	18.0 \pm 0.9	24.8 \pm 1.5
Total phenols (mg/L as GAE*)	3,600 \pm 180	720 \pm 43	189 \pm 15	1,227 \pm 123
Volatile compounds (mg/L):				
acetaldehyde	18 \pm 1	28 \pm 2	37 \pm 2	51 \pm 3
ethyl acetate	121 \pm 12	57 \pm 3	73 \pm 6	90 \pm 7
acetoin	101 \pm 8	1,096 \pm 66	352 \pm 18	69 \pm 4

*GAE = gallic acid equivalent

Figure 1
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Figure 2
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